

Dynamic Risk-Aware Reconfiguration in Coherent P2MP Extended Access Networks Under Time-Varying Demands

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Abstract

We study the dynamic P2MP light-tree reconfiguration problem under correlated, time-varying access demands. A greedy heuristic leverages a risk model and computes the access node assignments to light-trees, minimizing spectrum underprovision risks and reconfiguration penalties. Simulations show higher acceptance and lower blocking than static provisioning. ©2024 The Author(s)

Introduction

Traffic in access networks is unpredictable and prone to surges, with expected growth due to virtual/augmented reality and IoT advancements. Traditional metro-core nodes currently handle this traffic with several P2P links, but these setups lack flexibility and are costly with varying demand. Coherent optical P2MP transceivers are emerging as a viable solution: a single high-speed hub connects to multiple points using DSCM^[1], creating light-trees. This method improves aggregation efficiency and boosts multiplexing gain^[2]. For traffic going to the backbone, P2P transceivers can be deployed to forward aggregated data if necessary.

In access-metro settings, leaf demands fluctuate over time, necessitating dynamic resource management instead of static pre-allocations^{[3],[4]}. Dynamically modifying hub allocations and spectrum use can greatly enhance efficiency, but reconfigurations should be managed carefully to minimize control plane overhead and avoid disrupting services^{[5],[6]}. To strike a balance between flexibility and stability, we propose a risk-aware reservation approach that calculates the probability of future resource congestion by analyzing historical demand data from access nodes based on requested rates over time. Additionally, to ensure QoT despite non-linear impairments, we utilize a closed-form PLI model to evaluate OSNR^[7].

For the management of the networking devices we assume a centralized controller, which receives traffic demands from access nodes and computes new hub assignments, sub-carrier allocations, and ensures the feasibility of the connections. A lightweight agent running at each router applies these decisions by configuring the local P2MP transceivers, ensuring that light-tree parameters are consistently updated across the network. However, each such reconfiguration incurs control-plane overhead and risks service disruption, so it is crucial to minimize their frequency.

In this work, we address the dynamic reconfig-

uration of coherent P2MP light-trees under time-varying leaf demands. At each slot, light trees must be updated to reflect current traffic, while ensuring QoT through OSNR consideration and managing explicit penalties for hub migrations and spectrum resizing. We propose a risk-aware greedy heuristic that assigns each access node to a hub and allocates sub-carriers to maximize admitted traffic while minimizing reconfiguration costs. Simulations in a realistic topology show that the proposed heuristic fully serves the demands that static provisioning leaves unmet and reduces reconfiguration overhead by up to 12% compared to greedy provisioning.

System Model

Fig. 1: The extended P2MP architecture that makes use of light-trees associating hubs with access nodes from different rings/horseshoes

We consider an extended access-metro network in which multiple access nodes are arranged in ring (or horseshoe) topologies and end up at a metro-core node. Each metro-core node is equipped with I ports, each of which can host a single transceiver (Fig. 1). A P2MP transceiver at these nodes acts as a hub: it is the root of the light tree of W contiguous subcarriers towards its leaves (spoke nodes). Every leaf is equipped with a coherent transceiver that (i) receives its down-

stream subcarriers and (ii) and transmits to the hub for upstream transmission.

The time is slotted, and at the beginning of the slot t , each leaf $l \in \mathcal{L}$ reports its demand $d_l(t)$ (in Gb/s) to a controller. To meet this demand, a light-tree needs to be chosen, and consequently, a hub $h_l(t) \in \mathcal{H}$ must be determined.

However, the demands of the access nodes fluctuate over time. Let μ_l and σ_l denote the exponentially weighted mean and standard deviation of the historical series $\{d_l(\tau)\}_{\tau < t}$. Over a prediction window of T slots we approximate the demanded rate by a Brownian motion whose variance is $\sigma_l^2 T$. Under this hypothesis the probability that the demand remains below capacity K is^[8]

$$\Pr\{d_l(T) \leq K\} = \Phi\left(\frac{\ln(\mu_l/K) + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_l^2 T}{\sigma_l\sqrt{T}}\right), \quad (1)$$

where $\Phi(\cdot)$ is the standard Normal c.d.f. Fixing an overflow tolerance ϵ (e.g. 1%) and solving (1) for K yields the provisioned demand

$$\tilde{d}_l = \mu_l \exp\left(-\sigma_l\sqrt{T}\Phi^{-1}(1-\epsilon) + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_l^2 T\right), \quad (2)$$

The highest feasible modulation format that can be used on the path $(h_l(t), l)$ is determined.

$$m_l^*(t) = \max_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \{m : \text{OSNR}_{h_l(t), l}(m) \geq \Gamma_m\}. \quad (3)$$

With symbol rate R_s GBd, each sub-carrier in format $m_l^*(t)$ carries $b_{m_l^*(t)} R_s$ Gb/s, so the number of required sub-carriers is

$$n_l(t) = \left\lceil \frac{\tilde{d}_l(t)}{b_{m_l^*(t)} R_s} \right\rceil. \quad (4)$$

Allcating the aforementioned number of subcarriers for a given node guarantees that

$$\Pr\{d_l(T) > \tilde{d}_l\} \leq \epsilon. \quad (5)$$

Traffic spikes can exceed \tilde{d}_l , possibly requiring adjustments. Our model considers altering sub-carrier allocation is more effective than shifting a leaf to a different hub (light-tree). Adjusting sub-carriers on the current light tree is straightforward: it only requires activating or deactivating subcarriers in the existing optical link, involves minimal control plane signaling, enables almost real-time bandwidth adjustments, and can be done simultaneously for multiple light-trees.

Conversely, moving a leaf to a different hub necessitates altering the current light-tree and establishing a new structure. This involves several steps, such as redirecting paths and assigning new subcarriers, which can result in substantial delays. These delays are primarily due to the extensive reconfiguration required throughout the process.

Risk-Aware Reconfiguration Heuristic

At the beginning of every slot t the algorithm receives the *risk-guarded* demand vector $\{\tilde{d}_l\}$ obtained from (2) together with the incumbent allocation $\{h_l(t-1), x_l(t-1)\}$. Its goal is to maximise the traffic admitted in the current slot while (i) keeping the spectrum used by every hub within the limit W and (ii) minimising the cost of resizes and hub migrations.

For each access leaf l the number of subcarriers that guarantees its guarded demand is

$$n_l(t) = \left\lceil \tilde{d}_l / (b_{m_l^*} R_s) \right\rceil, \quad (6)$$

where m_l^* is the highest modulation format that satisfies the OSNR constraint in (3).

Each hub h reports two figures that guide the decision process. The spectrum left truly idle after the previous slot is

$$f_h^{\text{idle}}(t-1) = W - \sum_{j: h_j(t-1)=h} x_j(t-1), \quad (7)$$

whereas the spectrum that would remain *after* every spoke on that hub is resized to its fresh requirement is

$$f_h^{\text{idle}}(t) = W - \sum_{j: h_j(t-1)=h} n_j(t). \quad (8)$$

If $f_h^{\text{idle}}(t) < 0$ the hub cannot accommodate the new demand profile without either shrinking over-provisioned spokes or migrating some of them to alternative hubs. Spoke demands are processed in descending order of their demand $d_l(t)$. If $n_l(t) \leq f_{h_0}^{\text{idle}}(t-1)$ with $h_0 = h_l(t-1)$, the controller performs a resize of x_l with cost $C_{\text{resize}}|n_l(t) - x_l(t-1)|$. When this is not possible but $n_l(t) \leq f_{h_0}^{\text{idle}}(t)$, surplus slots are reclaimed from over-provisioned spokes on the same hub, without dropping any of them below (6).

If the hub node still lacks capacity, the algorithm scans the other hubs until it finds one that offers at least $n_l(t)$ free slots according to (8), has an available transceiver port, and satisfies the OSNR limit; migrating the leaf there entails the fixed migration cost C_{mig} plus the fresh allocation cost $C_{\text{resize}} n_l(t)$. If all hubs fail the test, the algorithm blocks the demand.

Upon completion, the heuristic revises the configuration $\{h_l(t), x_l(t)\}$ for all leaves. In the worst-case scenario, the algorithm checks all L leaves and scans up to H hubs. However, on average, fewer cases are inspected due to OSNR constraints, making this mechanism appropriate for millisecond-scale SDN control loops.

Numerical Evaluation

To evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed Risk-Aware Greedy heuristic, we simulate a realistic metro-core network derived from the TID

topology^[9], consisting of $H = 30$ hub nodes and $L = 300$ access leaves (10 per hub). Each hub is equipped with $I = 20$ coherent P2MP ports supporting four modulation formats (BPSK, QPSK, 8-QAM, 16-QAM) with OSNR thresholds $\{\Gamma_m\} = \{15.1, 12.5, 8.5, 5.5\}$ dB and symbol rate $R_s = 32$ GBd, yielding $W = 32$ contiguous subcarriers per light-tree. Leaf demands are generated in $T = 32$ discrete slots: at each slot t , demand $\tilde{d}_l(t)$ is drawn via the risk-guard model in (2) with per-leaf mean $\mu_l \sim \mathcal{U}[5]$ Gb/s and noise $\sigma_l \in \{2\}$ Gb/s. We discard the first 12 slots as warm-up and report metrics averaged over the remaining 20 slots and 5 independent runs per scenario.

In Figure 2, we present the average number of reconfiguration events per slot, including subcarrier resizes and hub migrations, is depicted against the risk tolerance ϵ . At ϵ close to 1, the short-sighted best-fit packing approach (lacking risk mitigation) triggers the most reconfiguration, as it adapts immediately to traffic spikes. In contrast, ϵ close to 0 holds the largest buffer, nearly eliminating resizes and migrations. A high risk tolerances reduce reconfigurations by 12% compared to $\epsilon = 0.01$. This demonstrates how the risk parameter can stabilize the network and lessen control-plane activities without affecting traffic flow. This is also vital for high-priority traffic. Here, all demands were fully met, unlike static provisioning that sets SC to peak demand, leaving 26% of nodes demands unmet.

Fig. 2: Average per-slot events (resize, migrations) as a function of risk tolerance ϵ .

Figures 3 and 4 present SC resizing and hub migration per slot, respectively, in three traffic settings with $\mu_l \in \{5, 10, 15\}$ Gb/s and $\sigma_l \in \{2, 4, 6\}$ Gb/s respectively and $\epsilon = 0.3$. The first 12 slots are treated as warm-up and data from the next 20 slots are analyzed. As demand mean and variance rise, performed SC resizing per slot and migrations also increase. SC resizes occur significantly more frequently than migrations, showing a preference for local bandwidth adjustments over full light-tree migration. This minimizes control-plane

load since managing subcarriers is less disruptive than P2MP tree reformation. In our experiments, migration remains almost stable with additional traffic variability, indicating that beyond a certain volatility (around $\mu_l = 15$, $\sigma_l = 6$), resizing handles variability without new hub connections. This implies that the algorithm prioritizes SC retuning at capacity limits, which is beneficial for quick SDN control.

Fig. 3: Average per-slot SC resizes at $\epsilon = 0.2$ for three traffic scenarios ($\mu=5, 10, 15$ Gb/s; $\sigma=2, 4, 6$ Gb/s). Slot 0 corresponds to original slot 12.

Fig. 4: Average per-slot hub migrations at $\epsilon = 0.2$ for the same three scenarios. Slot 0 corresponds to original slot 12.

Conclusion

We presented a dynamic heuristic that is risk-aware, designed for coherent P2MP extended-access networks, effectively balancing the trade-offs between blocking probability and reconfiguration overhead amidst variable traffic demands. Our simulation results reveal that integrating a risk tolerance in the allocation process, decreases the need for spectrum resizing and hub migrations in comparison to short-sighted, greedy provisioning approaches, while still fulfilling demands not met by static provisioning. These results highlight the promise of integrating risk-awareness into SDN-controlled optical access-metro networks to ensure efficient and stable resource utilization within realistic operational timescales.

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